

Faculty Development for Engineering Professors: A Course Integrating Active Learning and Digital Technologies

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Abstract

This paper synthesizes the authors' years of experience in training university faculty, particularly those teaching in Exact Sciences and Technology. It presents the theoretical foundations of the pedagogical approaches adopted in these training programs, emphasizing learning theories that guide the development of didactic strategies to promote meaningful learning. Additionally, it discusses the use of digital resources as essential tools for planning innovative teaching practices in both in-person and virtual environments. Within this context, the paper presents a teacher training course developed and implemented at the authors' institutions, designed to be replicable across higher education institutions. The course aims to empower professors to create and deliver learning environments in both in-person and online education, integrating theoretical foundations, active learning, and technological mediation.

Keywords: Active Learning; Teacher Training; Faculty development; Educational Technology.

1 Introduction

In recent years, particularly since 2019, due to the new curricular guidelines for undergraduate Engineering programs (Brasil, 2019), many Engineering schools have been facing the pedagogical challenge of training their faculty to shift their teaching paradigms, from a directive pedagogy, which emphasizes content transmission, to a teaching process focused on the development of skills and competencies, where the professor acts as a facilitator and students become the central agents of the learning process.

Reflecting on the training of engineering educators first requires an understanding of teaching in higher education more broadly, as well as of the current contexts and conditions under which university faculty work. The French university model, implemented in Brazil in 1808 with the arrival of the Portuguese royal family, contributed to shaping a teaching profile focused on professional expertise, where teaching consisted mainly of delivering lectures or presentations on specific subjects (Masetto, 1998). As a result, to this day, most Brazilian university professors are highly qualified and are master's and doctoral degree holders in their fields of expertise, yet they become teachers more by circumstance than by intentional preparation. In the specific case of engineering education, what we often see is an engineer-who-teaches, rather than a professionally trained engineering educator (Villas-Boas, Booth, Mesquita, & Lima, 2016, p. 484).

It is evident that, for many instructors, adopting an innovative pedagogical practice remains a significant challenge. This transition requires overcoming the barriers of "certainties," centralized "attention," and the notion of knowledge as "consolidated" and solely held by the teacher. However, in an era of connectivity, where knowledge is constantly being constructed and renewed, the learning process must be intrinsically linked to innovation, interaction, collaboration, discovery, and to strategies and methods that view students' questions as potential starting points for knowledge construction.

(Re)thinking teaching and learning processes, with an emphasis on the quality of professional and civic education of future engineers in Brazilian Engineering schools, is an urgent task. Otherwise, we risk contributing to the training of underqualified professionals, whose knowledge and practices may be inadequate in the face of rapid advancements in the world of work. A clear example of this can be seen in many undergraduate Engineering programs in the country, where, despite the new National Curricular Guidelines, the design of curricula and courses, as well as lesson planning, still fail to incorporate competency-based education, active learning strategies and methods, and the increasingly abundant technological and digital resources available.

Considering this reality, this paper presents a teacher training course developed and implemented at the authors' institutions, designed to be replicable across higher education institutions. The course aims to empower professors to create and deliver learning environments in both in-person and online education, integrating theoretical foundations, active learning, and technological mediation.

2 Theoretical Framework

An effective teacher training program must be grounded in processes of reflection in, on, and for pedagogical practice within the teachers' contexts of professional activity. This approach aims primarily to enable teachers, by learning to act and reflect on their actions, to develop a habit that facilitates the rupture with the traditional paradigm, one based on certainty in knowledge and practice. Within this perspective, pedagogical knowledge becomes a priority and an essential component of teacher education.

Regarding reflection, Ghedin (2005) proposes a transition from the epistemology of practice, as outlined by Schön (1992), to an epistemology of praxis, "since praxis is a movement operationalized simultaneously by action and reflection; that is, praxis is a final action that contains, within itself, the inseparability of theory and practice" (Ghedin, 2005, p. 133). For the author, the process of reflection must not be confined to the classroom but should also consider the historical and cultural conditions that shape the educational context, and the individuals involved in the formative process.

Thus,

A process of critical reflection would allow teachers to move forward in transforming their pedagogical practice through their own transformation as critical intellectuals. This requires becoming aware of the ideological values and meanings embedded in teaching practices and institutional structures, and engaging in transformative action aimed at eliminating the irrationality and injustice present within these institutions [...]. Critical reflection calls for a critique of the internalization of dominant social values as a way of becoming aware of their origins and effects. (Ghedin, 2005, p. 139).

It is also important to emphasize that

The pursuit of competent pedagogical practice, with higher-quality teaching, new alternatives for university-level instruction, and paths that lead to the construction and production of knowledge that go beyond the arrogance of crystallized knowledge, along with the implementation of experiences that seek to create new forms of teaching and research, are challenges demanded by the requirements of modernity. (Corteletti, Ribeiro, & Stedile, 2002, p.15).

Reflective practice enables teachers to engage in self-assessment of their beliefs and daily pedagogical practices, leading to changes in posture and interactions with different fields of knowledge, as well as to the problematization of the educational act. It serves as a means of empowering teachers to become protagonists responsible for guiding their teaching practice, rather than merely executors of predetermined tasks. Reflective practice values the teacher's tacit knowledge, not solely their academic knowledge, and recognizes the development of teaching practice as a continuous process to be refined throughout their professional life.

2.1 On Pedagogical Knowledge

In their teacher training process, professors must identify and understand their conceptions of learning, whether empiricist, aprioristic, or constructivist (Becker, 2012) and take a reflective stance toward them. Learning conceptions strongly influence the design of educational environments, whether in-person or remote, as well as the use of technology and digital resources. Creating learning environments where students are given space to act, analyze, discuss, problematize, and engage in the construction of their knowledge is a recurring theme in discussions surrounding the new National Curricular Guidelines for Engineering programs in Brazil. Considering the challenges faced by the academic community in keeping pace with the development of educational technologies while maintaining the quality of teaching and learning, we must find ways to better understand and explain the learning process, one that considers physical, biological, mental, psychological, cultural, and social aspects. To this end, it is essential, first and foremost, that educators have a clear understanding of their concept of learning, as it is this foundation upon which the learning environment is created, whether in face-to-face, blended, distance, or online courses, with or without the use of digital technologies and resources.

According to Elmôr-Filho, Sauer, Almeida, & Villas-Boas (2019), within the empiricist conception of learning, we find behaviorist psychology, represented by authors such as Watson and Skinner, whose explanation is based on the idea of conditioning, that is, learning is seen as a modification of behavior triggered by an external stimulus from the teacher to the learner. In this perspective, pedagogical practices are teacher-centered and rely on content transmission and control, aiming to produce systematic and operational changes in the environment and the teaching approach to increase the likelihood of desired responses. The student, in turn, is passive in the process, acting only in response to external stimuli provided by the teacher or the environment, and knowledge is understood as a sequence of stimuli and responses. This conception does not address the learner as a subject nor consider their entanglements, activities, or implications within the learning process.

The apriorist conception, represented by Gestalt psychology, particularly the work of Max Wertheimer, Köhler, and Koffka, places strong emphasis on perception and explains learning, according to Hilgard (1973), as something that occurs suddenly, through insight, based on an innate, a priori capacity that the individual inherently possesses. According to this theory, human perception is not merely the sum of sensory data but undergoes a process of restructuring that forms a unified whole, a *Gestalt*; it is not a collection of elements, but rather structured units, where the whole is greater than the sum of its parts. In this view, pedagogical practices, although seemingly learner-centered, are designed to allow insight to emerge through structured activities that highlight meaningful aspects to be perceived. Despite implying active engagement from the learner, the structure itself is predetermined and simply needs to be activated in a specific way.

From a theoretical standpoint, teacher training should also be underpinned by knowledge that serves as a foundation for teaching practices. Notable examples include Edgar Morin's Theory of Complexity (2002), Maturana and Varela's Biology of Knowledge (2001), and Piaget's Genetic Epistemology (1983), among others. These theoretical frameworks offer new perspectives emerging from scientific thought for investigating language, learning, and knowledge construction. They also establish a clear connection between cognition, learning, and life.

According to Bordenave and Pereira (2001, p. 28), "learning is the set of mechanisms that the organism activates to adapt to its environment." These authors highlight as a key point that:

in this same sense, it can be inferred that learning is an integrated process in which the whole person (intellect, emotions, muscular system) is organically engaged. In other words, learning is a qualitative process through which the individual becomes better prepared for new learning experiences. It is not, therefore, a quantitative increase in knowledge, but a structural transformation of the person's intelligence. (Bordenave & Pereira, 2001, p. 25).

According to the aforementioned authors, we can infer that learning depends on certain conditions to take place: the presence of a problem to be solved, which demands the engagement of an individual motivated to resolve it, thereby triggering attempts at action that bring them closer to their goal and to the learning objects defined by the contours of the problem. Furthermore, each new learning experience relies on prior knowledge, on solutions that have already been developed and internalized. Throughout this process, we observe that, in addition to cognitive aspects, individuals — learners — undergo emotional processes. Emotions such as curiosity, tension, anxiety, enthusiasm, frustration, and joy, among many others, influence the process of acquiring knowledge, retaining it in memory, studying, observing, experiencing, and receiving feedback, all of which contribute to the structure of the learning process.

Contributions such as Vygotsky's (Pellegrino, 2000, p. 38) emphasize this conception of learning, as "human beings construct knowledge through history and culture, based on interactions with others and with the reality in which they live." Rogers also reinforces the learner's interaction with the environment, asserting that in today's world, change is constant, and thus it becomes necessary to facilitate both change and learning. For Rogers (1969 apud Bordenave and Pereira, 2001, p. 47), "[...] the only educated person is the one who has learned how to learn, how to adapt to change; the person who has realized that no knowledge is secure, and that only the process of seeking knowledge provides a basis for security."

In this context, Masetto (2012, p. 45) states that the learning process should be understood as "a process of growth and development of the person as a whole, encompassing at a minimum four major dimensions: knowledge, emotional-affective, skills, and values-based attitudes."

Based on these conceptions, teaching activities can promote active participation and engagement through the formulation of problems to be discussed collaboratively by those who are motivated and willing to construct their learning paths. Transforming the traditional classroom, which is characterized by low levels of student participation, an emphasis on solitary activities, mechanical content learning as the primary goal of teaching, and the mere "distribution" of knowledge, depends on several factors. However, the most critical factor is the willingness of both teachers and students to recognize and agree on the benefits of such changes. These transformations require a significant revision of both the teacher's and the student's roles.

Constructivist approaches have increasingly advocated for the teacher's role as a guide, questioning, reasoning, accepting constructive suggestions, rejecting negative attitudes, and valuing all responses. At the same time, they emphasize attitudes such as respect, generosity, humility, courage, and trust. The goal is to shape a curriculum that considers students' questions and interests, transforming it into something meaningful and fulfilling for them. As active agents in the process, students must engage and recognize the benefits of their participation.

When the teacher sees themselves as a mediator between the student and the object of knowledge, they use content and strategies to facilitate this mediation. But more importantly, they understand it as a personal relationship involving two human beings interacting, influenced by all possible socio-emotional as well as technical dimensions. This gives rise to the need for empathy between the actors in the process, which is essential for understanding and respecting the other person's challenge. Such empathy is vital to the success of the mediation process, fostering a genuine connection between both parties regarding the goals of learning. With a focus on intentionality and reciprocity, this connection enables the emergence of all other necessary elements throughout the learning process, where teacher and student act as co-constructors of realities that interpenetrate and generate new knowledge for both.

2.2 Online, Remote, and Hybrid Education, Technologies, and Digital Resources

The COVID-19 pandemic, which physically separated students, families, and citizens around the world from 2020 to 2022, compelled schools and universities to (re)plan their activities to bring the classroom environment into the homes of confined students. The digital transformation in education, driven by the demands of the pandemic context, incorporated elements from the historical evolution of teaching and learning processes mediated by digital technologies.

Despite the technological possibilities that support the development of new distance learning models grounded in constructivist and socio-interactionist approaches to education, instructional and self-study-based models remain widely disseminated today.

When referring to Distance Education, we follow the definition provided in Decree No. 9.057, which considers distance education as:

an educational modality in which the didactic-pedagogical mediation in teaching and learning processes occurs through the use of information and communication technologies, involving qualified personnel, access policies, monitoring and appropriate evaluation, among other elements, and through which educational activities are conducted by students and education professionals located in different places and at different times. (DOU, 2017).

Currently, educational environments are being designed for both in-person and distance modalities. In Brazil, legally, only these two modalities are formally recognized. However, especially during the pandemic period, we have witnessed the emergence of a broader range of pedagogical approaches mediated by digital technologies. In this context, it is necessary to establish conceptual distinctions between Distance Education and Online Education. Distance Education is an alternative modality to in-person learning, while Online Education is a didactic-pedagogical approach and a phenomenon of cyberculture (Pimentel, & Carvalho, 2020). Online Education consists of a set of teaching-learning actions or curriculum practices mediated by digital interfaces that enhance interactive and hypertextual communicative practices (Santos, 2009).

In 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, many educational institutions adopted the model of "Remote Teaching," consisting of real-time classes delivered via video or web conferencing platforms. By 2021, institutions began transitioning to a format in which in-person classes are simultaneously broadcast to students who are unable to be physically present. This format has come to be known as "Hybrid Teaching," although this terminology is still debated among experts.

Online Education can encompass all these forms of technology-mediated instruction as well as both formal modalities, in-person and distance learning. Within the in-person modality, part of the activities and collaboration between students and teachers may extend into cyberspace, using apps or the institution's Virtual Learning Environment (VLE).

In Pimentel and Carvalho (2020), the "Principles of Online Education" are presented to propose alternative didactic-pedagogical practices for both the in-person (with technological mediation) and distance learning modalities. These principles are interconnected, interdependent, and form a coherent set of conceptions and actions necessary to implement Online Education effectively. For instance, collaborative learning cannot be fostered without genuine dialogue; to promote collaboration and co-authorship, active teacher mediation is essential; authorial activities only make sense when knowledge is conceived as an open work, among other key relationships.

Within the context of Online Education, collaborative practices can be mediated by software that enables cooperation, communication, and coordination. For each of these three dimensions of collaboration, there are both free and commercial applications available to support educational activities in in-person classrooms

(using computers or mobile devices) or in remote learning scenarios (where students are geographically dispersed but connected via the internet). Teachers must be familiar with these technologies in order to integrate them into their instructional planning and adopt active learning strategies mediated by digital technologies. In doing so, it becomes possible to enhance the learning process through interaction and authorship.

3 The Teacher Training Course

We present below a proposal for a teacher training course, based on the training courses offered at the authors' institutions. As previously mentioned, the purpose of the course is to equip engineering faculty to design and facilitate learning processes in both in-person and online environments, integrating theoretical foundations, active learning strategies, and digital mediation. The course addresses a critical gap: most engineers who transition to academia lack formal pedagogical training, and many experienced faculty members still struggle to design online classes that are both conceptually rigorous and pedagogically coherent. Therefore, the course syllabus was designed to meet these needs and is grounded in the theoretical framework detailed in Section 2.

The proposed course aims to: discuss aspects related to contemporary teaching practices and student learning in different contexts; create conditions for participants to learn about the characteristics of distance learning and face-to-face learning modalities mediated by digital technologies; characterize the distance learning modality in terms of its foundations, policies and actors involved; provide participants with the tools to plan, develop, and reflect on pedagogical practices mediated by digital technologies, as well as to practice the use of digital tools and the institution's virtual learning environment; and be easily replicated in any higher education institution.

The course was designed using the flipped classroom pedagogical approach, in which participants will engage with readings, video lessons, and podcasts available on the course's Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) prior to the live sessions, in order to support the practices to be developed during class time. To ensure that participants experience active learning strategies throughout the course, the topics addressed in the synchronous meetings will incorporate various techniques such as Peer Instruction, Minute Paper, Jigsaw, and Think-Pair-Share, using free software tools to support the activities, such as Socrative, Mentimeter, Google Drive for collaborative texts, and breakout rooms in the web conferencing platform.

Table 1 presents the structure of the eight sessions, which can be offered in a synchronous format using web conferencing software such as Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, or Zoom. Each session lasts 2 and a half hours.

Table 1. Topics to be addressed in the sessions of the proposed course.

Synchronous session	Topics covered
1	Foundations of Distance Education and Online Education.
2	Planning online courses in light of the foundations of Distance Education, Online Education, and Active Learning Principles.
3	Course organization in the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE)
4	VLE tools for practical activities.
5	Curation and development of digital teaching materials.
6	Apps to enhance online classes.
7	Active learning strategies supported by digital technologies.
8	Assessment for Online Education

Upon completion of the training, it is expected that participating instructors will demonstrate the development of digital competencies, having experienced the learning process from the perspective of a student. Furthermore, the topics covered throughout the course will support the planning of lessons that incorporate diverse strategies aligned with the context of Online Education.

While the eight-session course equips participants with the essential knowledge, skills, and digital competencies required to design rigorous online and blended classes, sustained improvement in teaching practice depends on support structures that extend beyond the classroom. The next section, therefore, outlines a set of complementary faculty-development actions that deepen, disseminate, and institutionalise the impact of the training.

4 Complementary Faculty-Development Actions

In addition to a teacher training course for engineering professors, with an emphasis on active learning and the use of technological resources, the researchers who developed this course believe that it is essential to implement complementary actions that strengthen pedagogical practice and encourage critical reflection on engineering education. The following initiatives extend the impact of the core course and align with the theoretical framework outlined in Section 2:

(i) Peer Mentoring: More experienced professors would accompany and guide colleagues at the beginning of their careers or in the process of methodological transition, that is, transitioning from so-called traditional teaching to constructivist teaching. This exchange between peers would favor continuous professional development and create a safe space for discussing planning that is more focused on active learning (Tillema, van der Westhuizen, & Smith, 2015).

(ii) Reciprocal Classroom Observation: Another relevant initiative would be cross-observation of classes, in which professors would visit each other's classes to observe the methodologies used to develop classes, provide evidence-based feedback on learning task design, and reflect on good practices. This experience would promote self-reflection and collaborative learning, in addition to bringing the teaching community closer together (Saborido, Domínguez-Montes, Benjumea, & González-Calvo, 2024).

(iii) Communities of Practice: The creation of communities of practice would also be strategic and especially relevant in the current context of implementing the new National Curricular Guidelines for undergraduate engineering programs in Brazil. In these communities, groups of professors, both from the same institution and different institutions, could meet periodically to share challenges, discuss solutions, analyze the results of pedagogical interventions, and collaboratively build knowledge about engineering education (Egwuonwu, Miller, Jensen, & Martin, 2022).

(iv) Targeted Micro-workshops: Short-term thematic workshops focused on specific topics such as formative assessment, the use of data from assessment instruments to improve learning, the design of activities based on new active learning strategies, the role of artificial intelligence as a collaborator in teaching planning, and inclusive strategies for diverse learners. Each workshop culminates in an action plan reviewed by peers (Zenni, & Turner, 2021).

(v) Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL): Engaging faculty in SoTL, for example, through action-research projects, strengthens the professional identity of the professors as reflective practitioners and nurtures a culture of pedagogical innovation in engineering education. Integrated into the proposed training course, these initiatives would expand their impact. Streveler, Borrego, and Smith (2007) note that SoTL typically starts with

an instructor's curiosity about student learning; its goal is to enhance learning by refining teaching, and its outcomes should enrich the literature on teaching and learning while contributing to faculty scholarship.

5 Final Considerations

The health emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated ongoing transformations in education, demanding the widespread adoption of digital technologies to ensure the continuity of teaching and learning processes. In this context, concepts such as Distance Education, Remote Teaching, Hybrid Learning, and Online Education became central to educational debates, demanding conceptual clarity and new pedagogical and digital competencies from educators. The training program presented in this text aims to address this challenge by offering engineering professors both theoretical and practical support for planning and mediating educational experiences. By engaging in active and interactive learning strategies, participants deepen their understanding of the role of instructional mediation in Online Education, strengthening their performance in both face-to-face and digitally mediated distance learning environments. In this way, the course contributes to a pedagogical practice that is more aligned with contemporary educational demands.

Although the course has already been offered experimentally several times, no systematic data collection has yet been undertaken. Consequently, this article focuses on documenting the instructional design rather than evaluating its effectiveness. The next step will be a mixed-methods study that will (i) administer pre- and post-course surveys to measure self-reported gains in digital-pedagogy competence, (ii) analyse artefacts produced during the sessions, and (iii) conduct semi-structured interviews to capture participants' perceptions and recommendations. The evidence gathered will guide iterative refinements of the materials and will be presented in a future publication.

Paraphrasing Weimer (1990), improving the quality of teaching and learning processes through faculty development is well worth the effort. The first to benefit from this process are the students. However, faculty members benefit themselves greatly as well. Teachers begin to experience the satisfaction of a job well done, which is significant, as few professions offer the profound personal fulfillment that teaching can provide. Higher education institutions also benefit once they gain credibility and prestige. Instructional excellence is just as difficult to cultivate as excellence in research, and institutions that achieve it deserve recognition.

Ultimately, although not always directly, society as a whole also benefits. When educators teach more effectively, grounded in constructivist principles, focused on the development of competencies, and supported by technologies and digital resources, they contribute to better student learning outcomes. In doing so, they help to shape professionals and global citizens who understand the world around them and their place within it, and who take an active role in their communities, working collaboratively to make our planet more peaceful, sustainable, and just.

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